

Cultivating Ecocentric Machines: Changing the Direction of the Anthropocentric Lineage in Intelligent Machines

Didem Gürdür Broo¹ (Senior Member, IEEE), Joshua C. Gellers², Henrik Skaug Sætra³

¹ Cyber-physical Systems Lab, Department of Information Technology, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden.

² University of North Florida, 1 UNF Drive, Jacksonville, FL 32224, USA

³ Østfold University College, Remmen, 1757-Halden, Norway

Abstract— This article explores strategies for cultivating a paradigm shift in the engineering design of intelligent machines, moving from conventional anthropocentric priorities toward a more ecocentric orientation aligned with ecological ethics. Through a comprehensive literature review, historical patterns of anthropomorphism in intelligent systems are traced, revealing how human-centered considerations have persistently dominated machine design across eras. To disrupt this enduring lineage and integrally reorient technology innovation toward ecological balance, four targeted strategies are proposed: (1) adopting question-seeking and systems thinking; (2) designing integrated ecosystems rather than discrete networks; (3) balancing exploitation with exploration; and (4) infusing diverse perspectives through transdisciplinarity. By reforming engineering education and culture from the ground up, the creation of intelligent machines can be realigned to enrich our shared environment rather than simply maximize human primacy. This paper offers a constructive roadmap to transform the promise of increasingly autonomous technologies in the 21st century and beyond.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since antiquity, intelligent machines designed by humans have overwhelmingly reflected an anthropocentric orientation, being crafted to serve narrow human interests and emulate human capabilities [1]. This profoundly human-centered approach has yielded substantial benefits enriching our lives, yet also harbors grave risks if not tempered by ecological awareness and ethics. Next-generation intelligent machines, also referred to as cyber-physical systems, are expected to be connected, intelligent, and autonomous [2]–[4]. Some examples of these systems include collaborative robots, autonomous vehicles (cars, trucks, drones), smart cities and infrastructure, integrated transport systems, and so on. The new characteristics—autonomy, connectedness, and intelligence—are not only expected to provide high performance and safe operations but also to be trustworthy and sustainable. In the fast-evolving technological landscape, numerous industries are keen to leverage the potential of new intelligent machines and systems to augment production outputs. However, they often grapple with time and resource constraints, limiting the opportunity for a thorough reevaluation of earlier decisions, including investments. This situation calls for a paradigm shift in the design approach [5], [6], emphasizing sustainability and the integration of these systems into living and artificial ecosystems, rather than treating them merely as utilitarian tools.

This paper argues that instilling machines with a sense of ecological responsibility now represents an urgent imperative. We begin by reviewing literature revealing the dominant anthropocentric lineage in intelligent machines across history. The multidimensional risks of unbridled anthropocentrism are then analyzed, encompassing philosophical, psychological,

and environmental perils. Most importantly, targeted strategies are proposed across engineering education and practice to cultivate more holistic, ecocentric design orientations that decenter humanity's primacy. The paper offers a constructive roadmap to realign technological progress with the flourishing of human and more-than-human communities alike. It calls on engineers to look beyond narrow anthropocentrism towards designing machines embedded within, not extracted from, the interdependent web of life.

II. KEY CONCEPTS: INTELLIGENT MACHINES, ANTHROPOCENTRISM, AND ECOCENTRISM

To establish a conceptual foundation for this article, it is essential to explain three key concepts: intelligent machines, anthropocentrism, and ecocentrism. This section will unpack each of these key terms in dedicated subsections.

A. Intelligent Machines

Intelligent machines refer to systems that can accomplish tasks amidst uncertainty by monitoring their environment and adapting accordingly. The term encompasses technologies from ancient automatons to today's sophisticated AI. A key prerequisite for intelligence is the ability to sense surroundings and adjust actions based on that perceptual input. However, there is no universally accepted definition of machine intelligence itself. The lineage of intelligent machines traces back millennia, with early examples including the abacus, water clocks, and other devices incorporating programmed behaviors and responses. However, applying the label of "intelligence" relies heavily on contextual technological capabilities. A system considered intelligent in ancient times would likely not qualify as such today. Standards and expectations of machine intelligence have risen in parallel with innovations enabling more complex, flexible, autonomous capabilities.

This conceptual fluidity is reflected in competing perspectives on pinpointing the origins of intelligent machines. Some cite the abstract computational abilities of early humans. More common is acknowledging pioneering programmable devices while recognizing their limited intuitiveness per modern standards. Regardless, analyzing the evolution of intelligence in machines requires contextualizing each era's technological achievements.

B. Anthropocentrism

At the highest level, anthropocentrism represents a worldview positioning humanity at the center of moral consideration. It grants intrinsic value to human interests and abilities while regarding nonhuman elements instrumentally.

This has informed philosophy, ethics, resource management, and other domains.

In the context of technology, anthropocentrism manifests in design priorities and assumptions elevating human needs and desires above all else. It translates into intelligent machines crafted expressly to serve narrow human objectives, utilities, preferences, and capabilities without balancing broader ecological impacts.

The concept of human-centered design epitomizes anthropocentric approaches by explicitly prioritizing human ease, productivity, and satisfaction in how technologies are conceived and built. While enhancing usability and experiences, critics argue this mindset risks overlooking needs of marginalized groups and future generations. Anthropocentric machines pursue goals like profit, convenience, reduced labor, danger avoidance, dominance over nature, and likeness to humans themselves. They reflect the assumption that the natural world merits ethical concern only insofar as it affects human interests. Their design revolves around extending human agency without regard for ecological dignity.

Importantly, anthropocentrism should not be confused with human welfare. Machines could theoretically maximize prosperity for some while disregarding overall humanity's needs. And humans value nature beyond just material gain, complicating simplistic dualities. However, machines designed to serve transient resource extraction, power accumulation, or elite gain without balancing negative externalities still manifest anthropocentrism.

C. Ecocentrism

In contrast, ecocentrism advocates extending ethical consideration to ecological wholes, not just humans. It recognizes rights and dignity in collective systems beyond what serves human society. Nature's intrinsic value does not depend solely on human judgments or needs.

Ecocentrism is thus fundamentally concerned with ecosystems' wellbeing, not individual interests in isolation. It considers humans embedded within and dependent upon, not superior to, ecological networks.

While seemingly compatible with environmental ethics, tensions arise regarding where to delineate moral boundaries. Critics argue a rigid nature/culture divide ignores how technology is entangled with natural systems, especially in the Anthropocene. With human activity inextricable from nature, ecocentrism must evolve to accommodate this complex interdependence.

It will require expanding notions of moral patiency to artificial systems indivisible from Earth's unfolding planetary processes yet exceeding narrow definitions of "natural." Ethical egalitarianism must move beyond antiquated divisions given intelligent machines' growing symbiosis with environments. Researchers suggest ways ecocentrism could embrace this ethical extension to abiotic systems.

For intelligent machines specifically, an ecocentric orientation would deemphasize human interests in favor of enriching ecological health. It would question anthropocentric assumptions through holistic, ecologically inspired design. Rather than extracting value, such machines would cooperate within dynamic systems and contribute positively to collective goals. Their overarching purpose would revolve around

cultivating resilience and justice within the more-than-human world.

Ecocentrism provides an alternative vision for technology design where humanity shares concerns, not dominates them. Machines aligned with this ethos would promote flourishing across life, privilege no single entity intrinsically, and integrate harmoniously within the communities that lend existence meaning.

III. THE ENDURING ANTHROPOCENTRIC LINEAGE

Anthropomorphism has been a persistent theme throughout the long history of intelligent machines. As will be explored in this section, though the particulars have evolved across eras, the core orientation toward designing these technologies to serve human needs, mimic human capabilities, and interact with people in humanlike ways has remained strikingly constant.

A. A Selective History of Anthropomorphic Machines

Engineers have long designed technologies and technological products like intelligent machines with humanlike essences to serve anthropocentric goals.

The following examples provide a selective overview:

- Ancient automatons like Philo's automatic wine-pouring maid (250 BCE) exemplified early efforts to create humanlike machines catering to human needs and pastimes [7].
- Hero of Alexandria, an ancient Greek engineer, crafted remarkable automata in the 1st century, showcasing his pioneering work in mechanical devices. His creations strengthen the epistemological claims of mechanics, and to relate mechanical expertise to divine cunning[8].
- In 13th century Egypt, Al-Jazari – also the writer of the "Book of Ingenious Devices" – crafted water-powered servant robots [9] continuing this anthropomorphic motif.
- The ancient Indian text *Lokapannatti*, compiled between the 11th and 12th centuries CE, describes the creation of automated soldier robots known as "spirit movement machines" to guard relics of Buddha housed in a secret stupa [10].
- The creation of the Automata Cavaliere by Leonardo da Vinci in 1495 [11] reflects the prevailing anthropocentric mindset of that time, as it demonstrated the focus on designing machines for human amusement and fascination. This mechanical knight automaton exemplified both da Vinci's technical ingenuity and the tendency to develop technologies that entertained and served human interests.
- In 1725, Archbishop Jakob von Dietrichstein commissioned a mechanical theatre featuring 256 figures, of which 119 were animated. A powerful hydraulic organ provided background music and covered the noise of the mechanism [12].
- In 1921, Czech dramatist Karel Čapek popularized the word "robot," a term he coined in 1917 to describe the synthetic humans in his science fiction drama *Rossum's Universal Robots*. Čapek's intelligent machines, built

Figure 1. Anthropocentric lineages in intelligent machines. Some of pioneering anthropomorphic machines and literature which explains these machines and their human-serving functions and/or humanlike traits over the centuries.

as servants for their human creators, ended up revolting and destroying their human masters [13].

- Gakutensoku, often recognized as the first android, was built in Japan (1928) with unmistakably humanoid features.
- Early factory robots like Unimate (1961) focused solely on maximizing human economic productivity and profits.
- Today's AI assistants like Siri emphasize naturalistic voices and personae to be helpful, compliant, and ingratiating companions. Though limited in their scope and reasoning, chatbots exemplify how AI can be applied to offer humanized interfaces and experiences [14].

B. The Multidimensional Risks of Unrestrained Anthropocentrism

Throughout history, intelligent machines have been created as obedient servants and perfect soldiers, serving human desires and ambitions [1]. This anthropocentric orientation is evident in various forms, such as mimicking human behaviors, enhancing human knowledge, providing entertainment, and exploiting nature for human benefit.

While this approach has benefits like using robotics for therapy or industrial tasks, it poses risks without ecological awareness. Anthropocentric thinking can reinforce the belief that the nonhuman world exists solely for human use, neglecting its intrinsic value [15]. This perspective damages the environment and disconnects humans from the natural world, posing philosophical, psychological, and environmental risks.

Philosophically, creating machines for human dominance

perpetuates the idea that nature is solely for human exploitation, disregarding its worth or rights. Robots designed for human convenience reinforce this view and prevent ecological humility. This anthropocentric framing is observed in historical examples like Philon's automatic servants and modern designs such as KUKA's "Famulus" - Latin for "servant" robot [16].

Psychologically, human-like machines distort self-understanding [17]. As AI assistants resemble humans more, the illusion of their consciousness can lead to conflicts and harm. This is exemplified in the criticism of sex robots [18]–[20]. The empathy gap between humans and nature widens, impacting human-machine relationships and weakening empathy towards nonhuman entities.

Environmentally, anthropocentric designs worsen ecological devastation, enabling unsustainable behavior. This approach delays action on issues like climate change and alienates humans from nature. The resulting disconnection risks diminishing empathy towards threatened ecosystems.

The literature underscores the anthropocentric tendencies in designing intelligent machines. While offering benefits, this approach also presents substantial risks. Acknowledging the intrinsic value of nonhuman entities and promoting ecological awareness can mitigate these risks, fostering a more balanced relationship between humans and nature.

C. The Need for an Ecocentric Orientation

In contrast to self-centered anthropocentrism, an ecocentric orientation recognizes the intrinsic value of ecological wholes, not just human interests [12]. It treats humanity as embedded within, not separate from or superior to, nature. Intelligent machines designed from this perspective would be crafted to enrich our shared environment, not merely

extract from it. They would be guided by moral consideration of diverse ecological and social impacts, not just human desires. Their objectives would align with justice, sustainability, and safeguarding future generations of human and more-than-human life alike.

In essence, whereas the anthropocentric design of intelligent machines myopically focuses solely on human interests (to the minimization and erosion of others'), adopting a wider ecocentric perspective may serve to benefit both humans and nature. To sustain the existence of a range of lifeforms and allow nature to flourish, we must cultivate fundamentally ecocentric machine designs that enrich, rather than vitiate, our planet's ecosystems. This requires a profound mindset shift—prioritizing ecological wholeness instead of human supremacy. It means designing intelligent systems that serve to stabilize, rather than disrupt, the biotic networks from which we have arisen and upon which we depend. Recognizing the profound pitfalls of extreme anthropocentrism, we must start to envision technologies harmoniously embedded within, rather than extracted from and destructive toward, the existing natural ecosystems.

IV. STRATEGIES TO CULTIVATING ECOCENTRIC MACHINE

Shifting design of future intelligent machines from an anthropocentric to an ecocentric orientation requires fundamental changes in the mindsets and priorities of engineers. This section outlines four key strategies to catalyze this transition.

A. Strategy 1: Moving from problem-solving towards question-seeking

The formal training of engineers, in the modern sense, is only 150+ years old [21] yet we are required to reimagine the field in response to rapid technological changes [22]. Comparative historical research on engineering [23] reveals that even though the definition of engineering and engineering knowledge varied greatly over time and from place to place, a distinctive commonality existed—the commitment to technological change and focus on technical problem-solving [22]. Therefore, the problem-solving skills of engineers are invaluable and unreplaceable. Yet, in today's technology-driven engineering practices, problem definition and creativity are becoming as important as problem-solving abilities [4], [22]. While the future cannot be designed explicitly, the artifacts that we create today will partially constitute the future that is tomorrow [24]. Design is a way of organizing those artifacts, both human activity systems, and technologies, so that they may contribute to an envisioned future. Herbert Simon distinguished the natural sciences which are concerned with explaining how things are from design sciences which are concerned with how things ought to be [25] that is, with devising artifacts to attain goals. Different than engineering, the design discipline provides us a way to think unboundedly without being limited by problems. While designing incorporates analytical, synthetic, divergent, and convergent thinking to create a wide number of potential solutions, it is more than problem-solving. It is also question-finding.

Today's practices concerning the design of intelligent machines are focused on problem-solving, and they are not

able to support the level that is desired in reaching Industry 5.0 or Sustainable Development Goals, where design for benefitting society is the key. Therefore, we should start to focus on question-seeking, along with providing answers/solutions for these questions. Efforts like design thinking [26] and more-than-human design [5], [6] offer useful approaches along these lines. Ultimately, the question-seeking task is a great way to reach more ecocentric intelligent machines. The ability to ask questions—and even to ask difficult questions that may not have any set answers—is one of the most important skills to extend our long-term view beyond the current practices when designing sustainable and resilient future ecosystems.

B. Strategy 2: Moving from networks towards ecosystems

In engineering and computer science networks are very well-studied. The first computer network goes back to 1956 [27]. These connected computers later evolved into the Internet. Today, we are still working on connecting more computers, sensors, Internet of Things, vehicles, infrastructure, etc. to build new or enlarge existing networks. These entities use common communication protocols over digital interconnections to communicate with each other. Networks are based on protocols and exchange information/resources.

Ecosystems are driven by mutual purpose and include development actions [28]. Britannica defines an ecosystem as “the complex of living organisms, their physical environment, and all their interrelationships in a particular unit of space” [29]. Ecology science is the scientific study of how life forms interact and coexist. Ecosystems are dynamic and, more importantly, ecosystems function as one unified unit whereas networks do not need to have a common purpose and focus on integrations [28]. Ecological systems or ecosystems consist of all the organisms and the physical environment with which they interact. Current implementations of digital ecosystems [30]–[32] are limited to software and, regrettably, the definition of digital ecosystems is not reflecting the many opportunities that biological ecosystems present. Frequently the word 'ecosystem' is merely used for branding purposes without any inherent ecological properties [33], [34].

Many from engineering and technology domains agree that we should move towards more dynamic new ecosystems instead of only integrating existing systems through networks. For instance, just this year, the vice president of Gartner, David Groombridge [35] said that “self-managing physical or software systems that learn from their environments in the longer term, will become common in physical systems such as robots, drones, manufacturing machines, and smart spaces.” To be able to build these systems in the future, we should already from today start to think about how to enable our systems to be resilient, sustainable, and collaborative.

We should go beyond designing networks of intelligent machines and use natural ecosystems as inspiration for designing next-generation machines as constituent parts of larger ecosystems driven by prerogatives like maintenance, integrity, and preservation of diversity. This ecosystemic view could enable future intelligent systems to pursue their own goals while contributing to a common purpose.

C. Strategy 3: Moving from exploitation towards exploration

Another important strategy involves the interplay between exploration and exploitation. In different research domains from behavioral science to computer science, the exploration-exploitation trade-off is studied and used to explain different strategies. It can be related to exploitation versus exploration (in decision-making research) [36], [37]; focused versus diffuse (in cognitive research) [38], [39], intensive versus extensive (in foraging research) [40], local versus global (in memory)[41], and depth-first versus breadth-first (in artificial intelligence) [42].

While exploitation focuses on exploiting known opportunities, exploration searches for new possibilities. Seeking a goal under uncertainty is a ubiquitous requirement of life. Animals forage for food, territory, and mates; humans engage in a wide variety of search behaviors, from looking for lost items to finding opportunities or to seeking the meaning of existence. Search, experimentation, taking a risk, discovery, and innovation involve trade-offs between exploiting and exploring [43]. [37] well-known theoretical framework of exploration and exploitation focuses on understanding how organizations remain innovative and what role organizational learning plays in this process. The research findings show that to maintain competitiveness, organizations exploit their existing capabilities and expertise but also explore novel ways of doing things. While the exploitation strategies may help with rapid development and are likely to become effective in the short run, self-destruction is inevitable in the long run [37].

The reasoning behind focusing on exploration in the proposed project is not due to unsuccessful exploitation results in engineering; it is rather due to not enough exploration activities found in current practices. The current engineering environments in industry and academia are heavily restricted by many constraints, including those related to resources, finances, and culture, among others. Research from industrial organizations, technology and operations management, organizational behavior, and similar fields has focused on understanding the effects of these various constraints. The fragmented and conflicting findings show that constraints can both hinder and foster creativity and innovation [44]. To develop ecocentric design solutions, we need more exploration, and we need scientists, engineers, and innovators who relentlessly explore different domains, and dare to go after impossible ideas even when we know that there is a risk of failure. While exploitation is safe, exploration requires us to embrace uncertainty.

D. Strategy 4: Moving from monodisciplinarity towards transdisciplinarity

One way to explore new possibilities is to observe the world around us and transfer knowledge from different disciplines – such as ecological science to engineering. The concept of transdisciplinarity is defined as “a common system of axioms for a set of disciplines” [45] transcending the narrow scope of disciplinary worldviews through an overarching synthesis[46]. It deals with research problems that emanate from complex and heterogeneous domains [47]–[49]. Max-Neef [50] argues that “transdisciplinarity, more than a new

discipline or super-discipline is, actually, a different manner of seeing the world, more systemic and more holistic.” While interdisciplinarity serves to enable the construction of common models or transfer of tools between disciplines, transdisciplinarity goes one step further in the science/society interface [51], [52] and instead focuses on articulations, preserving the different realities and confronting them in a controlled way.

The 21st century is characterized by rapid change, uncertainty, and increasing interconnectedness [53]. Rapid change is due to the continuous technological advancements from higher processing power to increased data capabilities. Uncertainty is due to this continuous rapid change and unprecedented events, such as Covid-19. Interconnectedness refers not only to technological advancements such as the Internet for connecting people and computers, but also the interactions between machines. Moreover, the grand challenges of this century, including climate change (and associated extreme weather events), water scarcity, air pollution, forced migrations, poverty, deforestation, rising inequalities, pandemics, and more, are complex problems [2]. They encompass interdependent systems and pluralism of values within societies and thus require a holistic view. They simply cannot be adequately tackled from the sphere of specific individual disciplines [50] but require the consideration of different perspectives using multiple lenses.

Benyus [54] summarizes the reasoning behind looking at nature as an example by stating that “after 3.8 billion years of research and development, failures are fossils, and what surrounds us is the secret to survival.” Ecology-inspired design will be the practice of mimicking natural ecosystems in order to imagine and design new engineered ecosystems. It assumes that nature is creative by necessity and that over eons of time, it has evolved countless sustainable solutions as ecosystems [55]. Researchers from different disciplines are already working on adjacent ideas. For instance, Connop & Nash [56] see nature-inspired design as an antidote to urban built environments from an architectural perspective. Yuchi et al. [57] studied an ecology-inspired strategy for parent selection and applied it to numerical constrained optimization problems from a mathematics perspective. Intelligent machine design and development efforts should operationalize similar approaches to find the best cases and inspirations for ecocentric approaches.

To address the crucial role of industrial education in fostering the transition towards ecocentric machine design, it is imperative to emphasize a shift towards interdisciplinary and experiential learning methodologies. Education should prioritize the integration of ecological principles and ethical considerations into engineering curricula, encouraging students to explore the complex interdependencies between technology and the environment. This could involve restructuring existing courses to incorporate modules on sustainability, systems thinking, and ecological design principles. Furthermore, our new educational approaches should promote collaboration between academia, industry, and environmental organizations to provide students with real-world exposure to ecocentric design practices and challenges. By fostering a culture of innovation, critical thinking, and environmental stewardship within industrial

education, we can empower future engineers to create intelligent machines that prioritize ecological integrity and contribute positively to the well-being of both humans and the planet.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has advocated moving beyond anthropocentrism to develop intelligent machines empathetic to the more-than-human world. With worsening ecological crises, this philosophical shift becomes imperative. Our technologies can either conserve or disrupt nature based on the priorities we embed within them. To choose wisely, engineers must adopt systemic, ecocentric thinking that decenter humanity's primacy within complex living systems. The strategies here aim to spur this necessary transformation across engineering education and practice. Our machines must be crafted to dignify all life and mend, not amplify, environmental harm—enriching the beautifully diverse communities that lend existence meaning. With creativity and courage, the future looks bright for technologies designed in symbiosis with nature.

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